

Gis based site specific major nutrient maps and recommendations for coconut gardens

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Abstract

Spatial distribution of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium were studied from 99 coconut farmers covering 195 acres representing different irrigation situations in Chikkapattanager of Chikkamagaluru district, Doddaghatta of Davangere district, Siriyur of Shivamogga district and Madhure of Chitradurga district of Karnataka state, India. The gardens selected were aged 20-25 years with varying management levels. Standard technique of grid method of sampling at 50x50 m spacing was employed to collect soil samples from selected study area at two depths (0-30 and 30-60 cm) with geographical identity by GPS. The soil samples were analysed for major nutrients by following standard procedure. Across all locations nitrogen status remained low while that of phosphorus shared medium to high status in equal proportion. With respect to potassium, 68 per cent of the top soil had high status. Using these data on GIS environment, fertility mapping of each area was done. Fertilizer recommendations based on soil test values for each grid is employed to calculate major nutrients requirement for fertilizer application. The package recommendation and the site specific recommendation are compared. Rescheduling of major nutrients based on site specific variations of 0-30 cm emphasized slightly higher application (844 kg) of nitrogen and marginally less application of phosphorus and potassium. Study reveals the variations in application of nutrients providing scope for re-allocation of these resources based on site specificity. Depending on site specific nutrient variations, nutrient application advisories were recommended for farmers in each location.

Background

The coconut palm (*Cocos nucifera* Linn.), is a member of the family *Palmae* (palm family). In India, it is grown mostly along the coastal regions in almost 18 states and three union territories with an area of 2039.10 thousand hectares, an annual production of 14006.50 tonne per year and productivity of 6869 kg/ha (Anon., 2012). Karnataka stands third in the country in terms of coconut production (2,176 million coconuts) and occupies sixth position productivity wise. Major coconut growing districts in Karnataka are Tumkur, Hassan, Dakshina Kannada, Chikkamagaluru and Chitradurga, which together account for more than 85 per cent of coconut-growing area. Hence, it is very important horticultural crop having a very high impact on the economy of farmers of Hill, Southern Transition and Central Dry Zones. By and large, the crop is being grown with middle to less care. The perennial nature of crop, the tall upper canopy, unavailability of skilled labours, biotic stress etc paves way for not caring situations. The crop is grown in diversified soil and climatic conditions. Basically, the soils also differ with that of agro climatic situations and not possible to generalize the soil nutrient status as it is a dynamic factor. At present, there is a uniform recommendation of major nutrients to this crop across soils of various agro-climatic zones. The present recommendation for coconut is 330:200:800 g nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium per palm in two split dosage for all nut bearing trees. Well established yielding coconut gardens were selected across these agro climatic situations with an objective to classify the soil nutrient status as a part of site specific management and to understand them the variability of their fields for improving the garden fertility status for sustainable yields.

Methods

The study area (Fig.1) included Chikkapattangere of Chikmagalur district where tank fed irrigation is dominant, Doddaghatta of Davangere district enjoy the supply of tank irrigation around the year, Siriyur of Shivamogga district also enjoys the Bhadrha river water supply and Madhure of Chitradurga district with limited success of tube wells irrigation. A total of 195 acre representing almost 50 acre at a stretch in each location was chosen. The standard technique of grid (50x50 m) method was employed to draw soil samples from the selected study area. Each grid is recognised by its own GPS co-ordinate to make area geo-referenced. Further, using GPS co-ordinates, the base maps of the study area was developed by GIS software. After taking soil samples from each grid, the soil was dried, powdered and Figure1. Study locations in selected districts of Karnataka state in India analyzed for available nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium by following the standard methods of analysis (Jackson, 1973). Also with the help of soil analytical results for nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium on grid basis, maps were prepared using low, medium and high classification criteria for each nutrient on base map of each study location through GIS. Based on these values of classification, by adopting soil test value approach of fertilizer recommendations, each site is calculated further for fertilizers quantity. The package recommendation and the site specific recommendation are compared.

Figure 1. Study locations in selected districts of Karnataka state in India

Results

The location wise results are indicated in the following paragraphs:

Chikkapattangere: Status of nitrogen remained low in both the profiles studied. For top soil layer, 70 and 30 per cent of samples remained medium and high respectively for P and K status; at 30-60 cm depth, the phosphorus status remained same as that of top layer while potassium has only 40 per cent medium sparing the remaining proportion equally to high and low status.

Doddaghatta: Depth wise no variation with respect to nutrient status is observed. In both depths, N remained low, Majority of samples showed medium status (> 95 %) for P content while K content varied from medium (around 70 %) to high (around 30 %) status.

Madhure: The distribution of nitrogen over profiles had shown uniformity with low content. The status of P in top layer remained high (around 66 %) to medium (around 33%) and reverse trend is observed at 30-60 cm depth. Potassium largely remained almost medium (around 72 %) in top layer; at deeper layer of 30-60 cm became medium to low status.

Siriyur: In top layer nitrogen has shown low (around 62 %) to medium (around 37 %) status and nullified at deeper layer with low status. Phosphorus was high (around 74 %) to medium (around 26 %) for 0-30 cm depth, while at deeper layer remained largely medium. Potassium largely had medium status (around 80 %) at top layer as it moves to deeper sections it become almost equal proportion of medium and low status.

Table 1. Fertilizer requirement (kg) for the study area depending on status of nutrient on grid basis

	NITROGEN		PHOSPHORUS			POTASSIUM		
	Low status	Medium Status	Low status	Medium Status	High Status	Low status	Medium Status	High Status
Chikkapattangere	1750	0	115	672	204	0	2385	1046
Doddaghatta	1706	0	15	925	0	0	2430	930
Madhure	1750	0	408	636	0	307	2700	542
Siriyuru	984	506	30	204	470	564	2610	116
Total	6190	506	568	2437	674	871	10125	2634
Grand Total	6696		3679			13630		
Package recd.	5813		3720			13950		
Surplus application	884		-41			-320		

Based on these variations of major nutrient contents on grid basis, base map of study area is considered for further classification into fertility status maps and same has been drawn using GIS technology. Fertility status maps envisage that nitrogen status remained low while that of phosphorus sharing almost medium and high in equal proportion (Bopathi and Sharma, 2006) while 68 per cent high with respect to potash for top soil depth of 0-30 cm. Hence it becomes crucial to manage these elements (Mahesh Kumar *et al.*, 2015). Here based on package recommendations, soil test value approach is employed to make further calculations grid wise (Table 1). Usually farmers apply in the form of DAP, urea and muriate of potash. The total requirement of fertilizers based on package recommendation for these areas is indicated in pictorial depiction (Fig.2) respectively along with calculated soil test value approach.

Discussion

Bearing ability of coconut gardens varied from 60 to 110 nuts per year. It appears that management of crop with different approaches by farming community dictated these variations. Apart from water supply to the crop, nutrient supplement assumes important factor which vary from garden to garden (Sabitha Soman and Byju, 2013). The retention of nutrients at different layers in almost all locations is highly dependent factor by timely relevant cultural practises followed in these gardens (Dhanashekar Pandiyan and Mohamed Harron, 2014; Shetty *et al.*, 2008).

Figure 1. Quantity of fertilizer required in traditional and site specific recommendations for coconut

Conclusion

It is observed from the above result that for coconut crop, across all locations, slightly nitrogen application needs to be applied more while potassium needs to be applied less with almost no perceptible change in application of phosphorus.

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